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COMPREHENSIVE INDICATORS FOR THE ANALYSIS OF OUT-OF- WORK BENEFITS

Introducing the Out-of-Work Benefits Dataset

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Abstract

In this InGRID deliverable we develop a new approach to the measurement of income replacement in out-of-work benefits. We present the Out-of-Work Benefits (OUTWB) dataset, which is part of the SPIN database at the Swedish institute for Social Research (SOFI), Stockholm University. The OUTWB dataset includes new synthesised measures on overall net replacement rates and progressiveness of income replacement in out-of-work benefits. Our synthesised measures of income replacement are based on data from the OECD Benefits and Wages project.

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of life or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

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Introduction

Challenges in research occur more often when we try to explain the ins and outs of a certain phenomenon rather than merely describe what is going on. This is particularly the case in the social sciences where experimental research designs seldom are appropriate. Due to the problems involved in organizing experiments and setting up randomised control trials, social scientists have to rely on other strategies to improve causal analysis of central processes in modern societies. One promising and frequently used alternative is comparative analysis (Liebersohn, 1987), which can take on many different forms (Ragin, 1989). In the area of social policy, it is common to use large-scale comparative research designs and various forms of quantitative analytical techniques to analyse data. Typically, researchers try to include as many countries as reasonably possible, and to use as many time points as readily available. However, lack of relevant and reliable comparative social policy data has hitherto constrained research, thus seriously restricting possibilities for comparative welfare state analysis.

The purpose of this deliverable is to discuss new and innovative ways of measuring income replacement in out-of-work benefits that help us to formulate and test more precise hypotheses about the causes and consequences of welfare states and of social policy. Replacement rates are commonly used in research to evaluate the performance of cash benefits, for example, in the areas of unemployment and social assistance. However, replacement rates are often based on calculations that involve too simplified assumptions, thus seriously restricting the validity of results. Comparative social policy research requires more detailed and accurate indicators on the institutional design of public programs for income redistribution.

This research task of the InGRID project uses data from the Benefits and Wages project at the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), available online at <http://www.oecd.org/social/benefits-and-wages.htm>. Based on OECD data we present a new comparative dataset that includes a variety of synthesised measures on income replacement in out-of-work benefits. All of these synthesised measures on income replacement are published in the Out-of-Work Benefits (OUTWB) dataset, which is part of the Social Policy Indicators (SPIN) database at the Swedish Institute for Social Research (SOFI), Stockholm University. SPIN data is available for download at <http://www.sofi.su.se/spin/>. The OUTWB dataset includes 39 countries for the years 2001-2011. Focus is on measures that capture the overall replacement rate of out-of-work benefits as well as measures that describe the distribution of income replacement across earnings-levels. Whereas the former dimension is often used in analyses of social policy and income distributions (Nelson, 2004; Scruggs and Allan, 2006; Bäckman and Ferrarini, 2010), *albeit* measured in more simplified ways, the latter dimension is often neglected in comparative research.

The deliverable is organised as follows. First we discuss possibilities and pitfalls associated with various types of social policy data. Thereafter we explain how income replacement in out-of-work benefits can be more accurately measured. In the following section we present some early descriptive results using our new data on overall replacement rates and progressiveness of income replacement in out-of-work benefits. We end the deliverable by offering some conclusions and suggestions for further infrastructure research on this matter.

1. The dependent variable problem

The difficulties involved in the conceptualisation and measurement of social policy are well-known among researchers (Clasen and Siegel, 2007). At least five different types of data are commonly used in comparative research to analyse the causes and consequences of welfare states and of social policy, namely expenditures data, case-load administrative records or social surveys, income distribution data, welfare state regime classifications and institutional indicators. Without any ambition to be exhaustive, we will review below each source of data, before explaining in more details how we may redefine our measures of income replacement in out-of-work benefits.

The main advantage of social expenditure data is availability. Comparative social expenditures data are indeed regularly updated and often readily available for cross-country research purposes. Expenditures data is usually collected from administrative records and continuously collected and published by several international organisations and government bodies, such as the International Labour Organisation (ILO), the OECD, the World Bank, the World Health Organisation (WHO), and the European Commission. Perhaps the most commonly used social expenditures data for research on affluent countries is the OECD Social Expenditure Database (SOCX), available online at <http://www.oecd.org/els/soc/expenditure.htm>. It includes public and private (both mandatory and voluntary) social expenditures as aggregates and disaggregated by branch, as well as by type of program.

Social expenditures are typically analysed as fractions of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and only occasionally analysed per capita (Castles, 2002; Kittel and Obinger, 2003; Swank, 2001; Clasen and Siegel, 2007). Despite its popularity in comparative research, data on social expenditures is problematic for a number of reasons (Esping-Andersen, 1990; Korpi, 1989; Gilbert and Moon, 1988; Castles and Mitchell, 1992; Clayton and Pontusson, 1998; Goodin *et al.*, 1999; Gilbert, 2009). Perhaps the most obvious drawback is that social expenditures are affected by several factors besides policy design. For example, social spending typically rises in economic downturns when unemployment increases, although the design of social policy remains constant or even becomes subject to retrenchment. Similar increases in social expenditures occur due to population aging. In addition, the most common denominator (i.e. GDP) tends to vary with business cycles, *albeit* in the opposite direction to that of social spending.

Although parts of the problems associated with data on social expenditures are avoided or downplayed by relating social spending to welfare needs, such sophisticated standardisation procedures are only available for clearly demarcated social risks that are closely tied to a particular policy program or a distinct set of social benefits. This is, for example, the case of old-age pensions and unemployment benefits, where social expenditures on retirement schemes and out-of-work programs quite easily can be divided by the number of people above pension age or the number of unemployed people. However, despite standardisation by welfare needs, it is almost impossible to take benefit duration into consideration, something that severely may distort empirical findings. Another obstacle is the general neglect of the fiscal welfare state, for example, in the form of tax expenditures (Howard, 1997; Ferrarini *et al.*, 2012) and tax claw-backs of transfer income (Adema, 2001; Adema and Ladaique, 2005; Ferrarini and Nelson, 2003). Changes in income taxation are generally not captured in analyses of social expenditures. However, both the OECD and the European Statistical Agency (Eurostat) have comparative data on net social expenditure, but only for a few years. In addition, Eurostat data on

net social expenditure should be analysed with caution due to the methods involved in tax simulations for some countries (Eurostat, 2009).

Case-load statistics from administrative records or social surveys are gaining popularity in comparative social policy research (Gallie and Paugam 2000; Arents *et al.*, 2002; Prinz, 2003; Immervol *et al.*, 2004; Erlinghagen and Knuth, 2010; De Deken and Clasen, 2011). However, data availability is not as good as for social expenditures. Although case-load statistics can be valuable for some research purposes (Oorschot, 2013), data generally suffer from program overlaps and inconsistencies in administrative categories between countries and over time (De Deken and Clasen, 2013).

Another source for comparative data on social policy is international income distribution surveys, such the European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC) as well as the harmonised national income surveys published by the Luxembourg Income Study (LIS). Data from income distribution surveys are sometimes used to calculate various measures of benefit generosity (Sainsbury and Morissens, 2002). Also here, there are problems of inconsistencies in administrative categories between country datasets and over time, meanwhile we typically lack information on benefit duration. Income distribution surveys often ask respondents only about their yearly income, disregarding the extent to which out-of-work benefits are received for one or a few months, or a whole year. In addition, household income from benefit programs is often misreported in social surveys, at least when placed in comparison with expenditures data from national accounts (Behrendt, 2002).

Due to the problems involved in comparative research to conceptualise and measure social policy, it is common among researchers to use a regime-based approach where outcomes are interpreted along the lines of broader social policy model types or institutional categories. By necessity, welfare state regime-based analyses are performed at very high levels of theoretical and empirical abstraction. Although the categorisation of countries into different welfare state regimes has provided valuable insights into the basic principles of social policy, the analytical grid is often too coarse for causal analysis. Nor is there any agreement about the exact number or nature of separate regimes or the categorisation of countries into different social policy model types (Abrahamsson, 1999; Arts and Gelissen, 2002). Quite often, researchers simply use the three worlds of welfare capitalism defined by Esping-Andersen (1990), perhaps adding an additional welfare state regime for Southern Europe (Ferrera, 1996) and another one for Central and Eastern European countries (Fenger, 2007). However, no matter the regime typology used, differences across countries that are grouped together are obscured, something that seriously restricts the amount of variation in our key variable. Furthermore, regime classifications seldom change over time. Although social policies in most instances change relatively slowly (Pierson, 1996) and system shifts modifying earlier classifications seldom occur (Korpi, 2001), social policies are far from being 'frozen' in time and space. We simply need more refined measures that capture changes to welfare states that indeed occur, although they are often gradual rather than fundamental in nature. Instead of regime based analyses, one alternative here is to use institutional data that in detail describes the legislative framework that governs social policy programs.

Institutional policy data is typically based on theories about social citizenship where legislative frameworks define the rights and duties of citizens (Marshall, 1950). The major advantage of institutional data is the close resemblance to the actual content of social policies. By using institutional data we gain a more thorough understanding of what welfare states actually do for their citizens and what kind of support people should receive according to legislative frameworks. The downside is scarcity of data. Comparative institutional social policy data is often not ready made out there and available for immediate download. Instead a considerable amount of basic infrastructure research is required before analyses can be conducted. This involves, for example, the establishment of more comprehensive forms for measuring income replacement in out-of-work benefits.

One strategy that is sometimes used to overcome some of the disadvantages of social survey data and institutional data is to rely on so-called tax-benefit microsimulations, where the Tax-benefit

Microsimulation Model for the European Union (EUROMOD) is a prominent example. EURO-MOD makes it possible to analyse effects of taxes and benefits on household incomes and work incentives for many countries. The model is often used to estimate redistributive effects of social policies and to explore potential impacts of future policies. EUROMOD can also be used to estimate budgetary effects of policy changes and to stress-test tax and benefit systems. Although EUROMOD has facilitated much new comparative social policy research in Europe, one obstacle is that data span a relatively short time period. Currently, EUROMOD can be used to analyse social policies from the late 1990s and onwards. For earlier years, data is not available for all EU Member States. Another obstacle is the complexity of the simulation tool, which requires considerable investment in personal competence and skills to master. EUROMOD is available online at <https://www.iser.essex.ac.uk/euromod>.

2. Income replacement in out-of-work benefits

Social policies are often evaluated and analysed on three different dimensions; levels of provision, degree of coverage, and financing sources (Montanari and Nelson, 2013). Income replacement in out-of-work benefits belongs to the first dimension and shows how much money citizens are legally entitled to under various conditions. A common methodological approach is to use model family analysis and calculate levels of provision based on the rules set out in social policy legislation (Bradshaw *et al.*, 1993). Entitlements are here calculated for model family types that are considered representative for the rights and duties of social citizenship and for the distribution of social risks. By necessity, model family analysis involves various assumptions of the households for which benefits are calculated, such as household size and composition, age structure, labour market positions, work histories and earnings. Quite often, the amount of benefits is calculated at levels representing model families earning an average production worker's wage (Korpi, 1989), although wages in broader sectors of the economy increasingly are used as well (OECD, 1996). The amount of benefits received, for example, in case of unemployment, is subsequently expressed as a fraction or percentage of these wages.

The assumptions related to the earnings level of model families have been a matter of great controversy. Particularly the strong tendency in comparative research to base model family calculations of out-of-work benefits on only one or a few earnings levels has been criticised (Kvist *et al.*, 2013). One of the most challenging aspects of model family techniques is the great amount of work that surrounds data collection. As a consequence of limited resources for research, the number of model families is often severely limited. However, the decision to use only one or a few wage levels in data collection may in some instances be justified on the basis of cross-country comparability over time. If we go back in history and collect longer time-series of income replacement in out-of-work benefits, industrial workers is by necessity the only relevant aggregate to which comparable information on earnings is available. Nonetheless, it is evident that we fail to capture the true nature of existing schemes for income replacement by including only model families that are supposed to earn some kind of an average wage.

With the addition of more earnings levels in model family calculations of income replacement in major cash benefit schemes we need to develop new analytical tools to capture complex institutional structures in less complicated forms. Only with a few more earnings levels, the number of data points drastically increases and we run the risk of not seeing the forest for the trees. It is outmost problematic to use all this information in statistical regression frameworks to analyse causes and consequences of welfare states, at least if data are available only in its raw format. Here, we need a new analytical grid to condense a vast amount of institutional information into single indicators, without intruding too much on the validity of our income replacement calculations.

The alternative used in our project is to borrow conceptually and empirically from research on fiscal systems and focus not only on the degree but also on the distribution of income replacement across earnings levels. In fiscal research, the former aspect is at focus when the overall income tax rate is to be determined. The latter aspect is instead emphasised in research on income tax progressivity (Haughton and Khandker, 2009). Analogous to this research on income tax systems, we will establish new comparative social policy indicators on overall out-of-work net replacement rates and progressiveness of income replacement. Progressive income replacement occurs when replacement rates are higher for model families with lower earnings.

3. Overall net replacement rates and progressiveness

The overall level of income replacement in out-of-work benefits is fairly straightforward as it is defined by the arithmetic mean of benefits when entitlements are calculated for model families having different earnings. The distribution of income replacement is more complicated to measure and here we rely on the method to calculate income tax progressivity first suggested by Kakwani (1977). To fully understand the Kakwani index of income tax progressivity, it is helpful to have some basic knowledge of the Gini coefficient and the associated concentration coefficient. Both measures are widely used in analyses on income distributions. The Kakwani index of income tax progressivity is defined as the difference between the concentration coefficient of income taxes and the Gini coefficient of disposable income. The measure is positive for a progressive tax, and negative for a regressive tax. It is zero for a proportional tax. One advantage of the Kakwani index of income tax progressivity is that it can be used to distinguish between changes in overall income tax rates and changes in income tax progressivity as the two dimensions are treated separately. However, it tells us little about the potential impact of marginal changes in tax progressivity. In order to analyse whether changes in income tax progressivity or any other income component have a large impact on the income distribution we need to take also the overall tax rate or overall mean of the income component into consideration.

As noted above, we use the OECD Benefit and Wages dataset to calculate overall replacement rates of out-of-work benefits and progressiveness of income replacement. The OECD Benefits and Wages dataset uses model family techniques to calculate the rate of income replacement at different earnings levels. Three model families are included: a single person, a lone parent with two dependent children, and a one-earner family with two parents and two dependent children. The breadwinner is assumed to be involuntary unemployed for the whole year. The out-of-work benefit packages includes social assistance and associated minimum income benefits, housing allowances, child or family benefits, unemployment benefits, and tax expenditures of various kinds. Information about income taxation and social security contributions is also included in the benefit packages. A few notes on housing allowances are worth mentioning. Housing allowances often differ from other items in the benefit package since entitlements are set in relation to rent expenses of the household. The OECD uses a very simple and straightforward assumption where the rent level is 20 percent of the gross average wage, irrespective of earnings-level and type of model family. Out-of-work replacement rates are calculated for earnings levels corresponding to 0.00, 0.01, ..., 2.00 times an average wage. Thus, for each country and year the OECD Benefit and Wages data matrix includes 603 different replacement rates (three model families and 201 earnings levels). At lower earnings levels, the benefit package usually includes any means- or income-tested benefits to which the model family is entitled, such as social assistance and housing allowances. As the earnings levels of the model families' increase, low-income targeted benefits are gradually phased out.

The overall replacement rate of out-of-work benefits is simply defined as the average income replacement of model families at different earnings levels. The progressiveness of income replacement in out-of-work benefits is the concentration coefficient of replacement rates when model families are ranked according to their earnings level. Since the distribution of earnings is exactly the same across countries and over time, we do not have to subtract the Gini coefficient of earnings from

the concentration coefficient of out-of-work replacement rates. However, for ease of presentation, we multiply the concentration coefficient of income replacement by a factor of -1.0. The progressiveness of income replacement in out-of-work benefits ranges between values of -1 and +1. Positive values indicate that income replacement is higher among model families with lower earnings, and that progressiveness is strong. Negative values indicate that income replacement is higher among model families with higher earnings, and consequently regressive. Values close to zero suggest that the rate of income replacement is evenly distributed across earnings levels. For both the overall rate and the progressiveness of income replacement in out-of-work benefits, all benefits are measured after tax and social security contributions.

4. A short note on the issue of income packaging

One of the ultimate goals of academic research is to provide new knowledge that can help societies to progress. What kind of advice and expertise that scholars can deliver depend of course on the research questions addressed and the theoretical underpinnings of each study. In research on social benefit programs it is seldom recognised and clearly outspoken that there are at least two separate approaches to calculate income replacement that address fundamentally different questions (Ferrarini *et al.*, 2013). Possibilities for policy inference and guidelines are to large extent dependent on which approach that is adopted.

When the main objective is to evaluate the income position of particular vulnerable groups, the issue of income packaging is usually brought into the foreground. Here it is recognised that people simultaneously may receive benefits from several different types of programs and that replacement rates should reflect this interplay between benefits. The income packaging approach to social policy analysis is fruitfully used when the main research objective is to analyse how welfare states provide an acceptable standard of living independently of markets. However, the method is less precise when causal processes of institutional change are in focus. By stacking different benefits into a single scale in an income package, we often conceal important differences between programs that are of relevance for our understanding of institutional change. Here, it may be more fruitful to analyse each program separately and calculate the extent to which single benefits replace income at different earnings levels.

5. The Out-of-Work Benefits (OUTWB) Dataset

Since analyses on the income position of vulnerable families as well as causal analyses on institutional change in single benefit programs would benefit from social policy data that distinguishes between overall replacement rates and progressiveness of income replacement, the OUTWB dataset includes separate indicators reflecting a variety of different benefit packages. More precisely, for each model family we calculate income replacement based on benefit packages that include (a) only unemployment benefits, (b) unemployment benefits and social assistance, and (c) unemployment benefits, social assistance and housing allowances. Child benefits are included in all analyses where they are applicable (i.e. for model families with children). To allow for even greater flexibility in policy analysis, income replacement in out-of-work benefits are calculated at different earnings intervals of model families, including earnings ranging from 33-200, 50-200 and 67-200 percent of an average wage. In total, the OUTWB dataset includes 92 different variables on income replacement in out-of-work benefits. Table 1 shows the variable list of the Out-of-work Benefits Dataset, and abbreviations are shown in Table 2.

Table 5.1 Variable list of the Out-of-work Benefits (OUTWB) Dataset

Year	Country	pg_ush_33_si	pg_us_33_si
pg_u_33_si	pg_ushc_33_lp	pg_usc_33_lp	pg_uc_33_lp
pg_u_33_lp	pg_ushc_33_fa	pg_usc_33_fa	pg_uc_33_fa
pg_u_33_fa	pg_ush_67_si	pg_us_67_si	pg_u_67_si
pg_ushc_67_lp	pg_usc_67_lp	pg_uc_67_lp	pg_u_67_lp
pg_ushc_67_fa	pg_usc_67_fa	pg_uc_67_fa	pg_u_67_fa
pg_ush_50_si	pg_us_50_si	pg_u_50_si	pg_ushc_50_lp
pg_usc_50_lp	pg_uc_50_lp	pg_u_50_lp	pg_ushc_50_fa
pg_usc_50_fa	pg_uc_50_fa	pg_u_50_fa	rr_u_33_si
rr_us_33_si	rr_ush_33_si	rr_u_33_lp	rr_uc_33_lp
rr_usc_33_lp	rr_ushc_33_lp	rr_u_33_fa	rr_uc_33_fa
rr_usc_33_fa	rr_ushc_33_fa	rr_u_50_si	rr_us_50_si
rr_ush_50_si	rr_u_50_lp	rr_uc_50_lp	rr_usc_50_lp
rr_ushc_50_lp	rr_u_50_fa	rr_uc_50_fa	rr_usc_50_fa
rr_ushc_50_fa	rr_u_67_si	rr_us_67_si	rr_ush_67_si
rr_u_67_lp	rr_uc_67_lp	rr_usc_67_lp	rr_ushc_67_lp
rr_u_67_fa	rr_uc_67_fa	rr_usc_67_fa	rr_ushc_67_fa
pg_ushc_33	pg_usc_33	pg_u_33	pg_uc_33
pg_ushc_50	pg_usc_50	pg_u_50	pg_uc_50
pg_ushc_67	pg_usc_67	pg_u_67	pg_uc_67
rr_ushc_33	rr_usc_33	rr_u_33	rr_uc_33
rr_ushc_50	rr_usc_50	rr_u_50	rr_uc_50
rr_ushc_67	rr_usc_67	rr_u_67	rr_uc_67

Table 5.2 Abbreviations in the Out-of-work Benefits (OUTWB) Dataset

pg	Progressivity
rr	Net replacement rate
u	Unemployment benefits
s	Social assistance and other minimum income benefits
h	Housing benefits
c	Child and Family benefits
si	Single person
lp	Lone parent
fa	Two parent family
33	Benefits calculated for model families earning 33, 34, ..., 200 percent of an average wage
50	Benefits calculated for model families earning 50, 51, ..., 200 percent of an average wage
67	Benefits calculated for model families earning 67, 68, ..., 200 percent of an average wage
***	Variable names without abbreviations 'si', 'lp' or 'fa' are averages of the three model family types

6. Illustration of data and results

In order to provide readers some understanding of how OUTWB data looks like and how data can be used, we will in the following show some descriptive results. The illustrations of the data are far from exhaustive as the idea is merely to provide a snapshot of all information stored in the OUTWB files. Figure 1 shows overall net replacement rates and income replacement progressivity in out-of-work benefits as an average of model families earning 33 up to 200 percent of an average wage. Three model family types are used in this exercise; a single person, a lone parent and a two-parent family. We have pooled data for 2001-2011 and thus provide grand means for the whole period. The whole benefit package above is included in the analysis.

Figure 6.1 Overall out-of-work net replacement rates and progressiveness of income replacement in 39 countries, averages 2001-2011

Note: Income replacement calculations include three model families (single person, lone parent and two-parent family) and benefits are calculated at earnings levels of 33, 34, ..., 200 percent of an average wage. The diagonal line shows the predicted net replacement rate at various levels of income tax progressivity.

Overall net replacement rates and progressiveness of income replacement are evidently negatively associated, thus lending some support to the hugely influential, but nonetheless contested and disputed (Kenworthy, 2011; Marx *et al.*, 2013; Brady and Bostic, 2015), idea of a paradox of redistribution (Korpi and Palme, 1998). According to this paradox, the inclusion of middle class needs for income protection in the welfare state generates necessary political support for raising also minimum income benefits and other anti-poverty programs further up the income scale.

Figure 6.2 Changes in overall out-of-work net replacement rates and progressiveness of income replacement in 39 countries 2001-2011

Note: Income replacement calculations include three model families (single person, lone parent and two-parent family) and benefits are calculated at earnings levels of 33, 34, ..., 200 percent of an average wage.

Besides analysing cross-country differences it is interesting to study developments over time. Figure 2 above shows changes in overall net replacement rates and income replacement progressivity in out-of-work benefits as an average of model families earning 33 up to 200 percent of an average wage in 39 countries over the period 2001-2011. Once again we use the three model families above and concentrate on the whole benefit package. The most striking pattern is that both overall out-of-work net replacement rates and progressiveness of income replacement have been quite stable over the period, despite the recent global financial crisis.

One frequently debated issue in the comparative welfare state literature concerns possible convergence in institutional structures and whether welfare states are becoming more similar over time (Montanari *et al.*, 2007; Nelson, 2008; Starke *et al.*, 2008). Although OUTWB data presently covers only ten years of welfare state development it is interesting to examine whether the most recent development in out-of-work benefits shows tendencies toward convergence. Figure 3 shows cross-national dispersions in overall out-of-work net replacement rates and income replacement of benefits as above, and convergence is measured by the coefficient of variation. The coefficient of variation is defined as the standard deviation divided by the arithmetic mean.

Figure 6.3 Cross-national dispersion (coefficient of variation) in overall out-of-work net replacement rates and progressiveness of income replacement in 39 countries, 2001-2011 (index 2001=100)

Note: Income replacement calculations include three model families (single person, lone parent and two-parent family) and benefits are calculated at earnings levels of 33, 34, ..., 200 percent of an average wage.

There is no empirical evidence of convergence in out-of-work benefits. To the contrary, the general tendency is that overall net replacement rates and progressiveness of income replacement in out-of-work benefits have diverged and become more different across countries over the most recent decade. Particularly the coefficient of variation for income replacement progressivity has increased substantially, at least since 2004.

Since the same wage level is used in the denominator to calculate replacement rates at different earnings levels, it is not really meaningful to outright compare income replacement in out-of-work benefits across model family types. To perform such comparisons we first need to equalise benefits to household needs (Nelson, 2013), something that is beyond this presentation of the OUTWB dataset. Here, we will merely use country rankings and analyse the extent to which objectives of countries to cater for unemployed people differ depending on family circumstances.

One issue of great interest in comparative welfare state research relates to gender and whether welfare states differ in objectives concerning protection of male-breadwinner families and lone parents (Orloff, 1993; Hobson, 1994; Sainsbury, 1996). Table 3 shows overall net replacements rate by model family type in 38 OECD countries. Only data for 2011 is used. Cyprus is not included in this analysis because of missing data for 2011. For each model family type we calculate benefits at earnings from 33 up to 200 percent of an average wage. Countries are ranked from high to low separately for each model family and categorised into three equally sized groups: high, medium and low income replacement. Most countries perform equally across model family types and change ranking only marginally. However, some countries treat single persons, lone parents and two-parent families quite differently. Comparatively speaking, Canada and Lithuania, for example, score much better for the lone parent and the two-parent model families than for the single person model family. France shows the opposite tendency and ranks much higher when the analysis is restricted to a single person model

family. The lone parent model family is much worse off than the two-parent model family in Ireland, whereas the opposite is true for Slovakia.

Table 6.1 Overall out-of-work net replacement rates disaggregated by model family type in 38 countries, 2011 (countries ranked from high to low and categorised into three equally sized groups)

	Model family					
	Single person		Lone Parent		Two-parent family	
High	LVA	0.812	LUX	0.863	LUX	0.859
	LUX	0.808	CHE	0.827	DNK	0.836
	BUL	0.766	BUL	0.811	CHE	0.831
	ISR	0.762	SVK	0.804	SVN	0.805
	PRT	0.759	SVN	0.788	BUL	0.794
	CHE	0.734	LVA	0.784	LVA	0.776
	FRA	0.695	PRT	0.781	IRL	0.775
	NLD	0.686	NOR	0.740	PRT	0.765
	SVN	0.671	DNK	0.740	LTU	0.755
	SVK	0.644	ISR	0.726	NLD	0.747
	CZE	0.641	DEU	0.717	ISR	0.736
	DNK	0.613	CAN	0.714	DEU	0.734
	Medium	BEL	0.601	LTU	0.709	ISL
ISL		0.594	JPN	0.704	CAN	0.722
DEU		0.589	FIN	0.702	AUT	0.715
NOR		0.569	ISL	0.698	JPN	0.713
IRL		0.564	FRA	0.689	FIN	0.700
CHI		0.559	NLD	0.669	NOR	0.694
JPN		0.550	AUT	0.662	FRA	0.668
FIN		0.547	POL	0.662	CZE	0.641
EST		0.546	CZE	0.649	GBR	0.639
ESP		0.537	BEL	0.634	SWE	0.635
ITA		0.531	ESP	0.627	EST	0.633
CAN		0.530	ITA	0.626	CHI	0.628
POL		0.526	SWE	0.617	ESP	0.626
Low	AUT	0.520	EST	0.614	SVK	0.623
	HUN	0.502	CHI	0.610	ITA	0.613
	SWE	0.489	IRL	0.585	HUN	0.611
	LTU	0.441	GBR	0.584	NZL	0.565
	USA	0.441	HUN	0.583	BEL	0.565
	KOR	0.410	NZL	0.524	AUS	0.557
	MLT	0.396	MLT	0.509	POL	0.552
	GBR	0.395	AUS	0.488	MLT	0.521
	TUR	0.389	ROM	0.455	USA	0.457
	ROM	0.384	USA	0.440	ROM	0.433
	GRC	0.370	KOR	0.418	GRC	0.415
	NZL	0.355	GRC	0.415	KOR	0.398
	AUS	0.292	TUR	0.383	TUR	0.380

Note: Benefits are calculated at earnings levels of 33, 34, ..., 200 percent of an average wage.

Results may not only change depending on which model family type that is chosen for comparison. To some extent, the composition of the benefit package is equally important to consider. Particularly

the inclusion or exclusion of housing allowances can make a huge impact on the results. Figure 4 shows overall net replacement rates before and after housing benefits in 38 OECD countries. Once again we only use data for 2011 and Cyprus is therefore excluded from analysis. Benefits are calculated at earnings from 33 up to 200 percent of an average wage and for illustrative purposes we use averages of the three model families.

Figure 6.4 Overall out-of-work net replacement rates before and after housing benefits in 38 countries, 2011

Note: Income replacement calculations include three model families (single person, lone parent and two parent family) and benefits are calculated at earnings levels of 33, 34, ..., 200 percent of an average wage.

Overall net replacement rates change substantially in a few countries. After housing benefits, the overall net replacement rate is more than 10 percentage points higher in Ireland, Poland and the United Kingdom. It is between 5 and 10 percentage points higher in the Czech Republic, Finland, Japan and New Zealand. Here it should be noted that housing benefits and other forms of means-tested and income-tested benefits often suffer from incomplete take-up. In the OUTWB dataset we assume that all model families claim the benefits that they are entitled to. Any adjustments to non take-up would most likely reduce the difference in overall replacement rates before and after housing benefits.

7. Conclusions

In this deliverable we have discussed new and innovative ways to analyse social policy in comparative and longitudinal perspective. We have focused on out-of-work benefits and calculated various new measures on overall replacement rates and progressiveness of income replacement. We also introduced our new dataset on out-of-work benefits (OUTWB), which is based on information provided by the OECD Benefits and Wages project.

Many of the questions that receive great scholarly attention in the comparative welfare state literature require an institutional perspective where data in detail capture how policies are organised. Income replacement is an important dimension in this regard that deserves more critical attention, both in terms of conceptualisation and measurement. Particularly, it is relevant to distinguish between the size and the distribution of income replacement at different earnings levels. One alternative is to focus on overall net replacement rates in out-of-work benefits and progressiveness of income replacement.

Both dimensions may add to our understanding of the social and economic impact of social policies and how welfare states have developed over recent (crisis) years. Here we need to increase our understanding of the role of income replacement progressivity in the redistributive processes of welfare states, and how the distribution of benefits across earnings levels is related to the overall ambitions of governments to reduce income inequalities and alleviate poverty. Another issue of great concern is income packaging and how changes in single benefit programs affect overall replacement rates and the distribution of income replacement across earnings levels. Particularly the role of housing benefits deserves greater attention in this regard. Here, the assumptions used by the OECD in their calculations of entitlement levels should fruitfully be modified and tested for sensitivity. One starting point is to calculate housing benefits not only at different earnings levels, but also at different rent costs of model families.

The OUTWB dataset borrows extensively from data collected within the OECD Benefit and Wages project. For further information concerning the assumptions used to calculate replacement rates at different levels of earnings we kindly refer to documentation at the OECD. For information that more specifically concerns our synthesised measures of income replacement in out-of-work benefits we refer inquiries to the SPIN database at Stockholm University.

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Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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